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PROBLEMS OF ORGANIZING SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. The article describes the problems, importance and relevance of the organization of services in the digital economy. The data are compiled based on the author's observations and analysis of foreign literature. The methodological basis of the research was formed as a result of the study of theoretical and practical information, legislation and other legal documents, literary sources and publications. The research is based on the connections between theory and practice and made extensive use of analysis, comparison, and synthesis methods.

Keywords. Digital Economy, Service, Service, Provision Of Services, Factor, It-Technologies, Quality, Competition, Trade, Network, Development.

I. INTRODUCTION

The level of development of services reflects the socio-economic situation in the country.

Today, along with population growth, the demand for services is also growing. At the same time, we can see an increase in the quality of services provided to the population with the development of digital technologies. Nevertheless, we can observe some services' poor quality or non-availability in our country.

According to the World Bank, the share of services in the GDP of developed countries is 70-90%¹ is formed.

The share of services in the country in 2020 was 36.3%² is formed.

60-70 percent of the world's population is engaged in service³ is formed. 40-46% of services in the country in 2017-2020⁴ are formed.

Experience shows that 65-75% of total consumer goods in human life are services. Demand for services is growing, especially in the era of digital technology.

In the era of the digital economy, the penetration of various electronic devices into human life has emerged as a means of facilitating the satisfaction of some of their needs.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In their research, the following scholars have considered problems of organizing services in the digital economy: Makhmudov L.U., Rakhimov Z.K. [4].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the research was formed as a result of the study of theoretical and practical information, legislation and other legal documents, literary

¹ <https://data.worldbank.org/>

² https://stat.uz/uz/default/quarterly_results/5708-quarterly_results-2020_January/December

³ https://stat.uz/uz/default/quarterly_results/5708-quarterly_results-2020_January/December

⁴Data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

sources and publications. The research is based on the connections between theory and practice and made extensive use of analysis, comparison, and synthesis methods.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Digital technologies provide several conveniences to customers when using certain services. For example, with the organization of distance learning, rather than in traditional classrooms, electronic use of consulting services, remote ordering of services, etc.

Japan, Germany, South Korea, and the USA⁵In such countries, entrepreneurs recognize that it is convenient to use digital technologies to study their needs and develop goods and services to customers' needs by establishing direct contact with consumers. According to them, communication with customers through such technologies will further increase their confidence in goods and services and create opportunities for providing competitive goods and services.

In recent years, our country has also been providing various services using digital technologies. In particular, in the socio-economic development of the country, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev dated February 7, 2017, "On the Action Strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" PF-4947⁶The implementation of the priorities set out in has served as an impetus for the development of digital technologies. In particular, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 15, 2021, "On measures to further improve the system of rating assessment of the state of development of the digital economy and e-government" No 373⁷Following the Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" in our country, a set of measures in the field of public education, public services, judiciary, finance and banking to digitize sectors and regions of the economy, the introduction of public information systems and electronic services, as well as the widespread use of digital technologies. events ⁸it is possible to understand the importance of digital technology today in implementation.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev dated January 28, 2022, "On the Development Strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" PF-60⁹Measures for the development of new socio-economic spheres of the Republic of Uzbekistan together with digital technologies for 2022-2026 have been identified.

It should be noted that digital technologies provide ample opportunities to improve the living standards of the population of our country and increase transparency and quality in all areas, including the provision of services to the population.

Today, there are some shortcomings in the provision of quality service based on digital technologies in practice. These include the lack of quality Internet services in all regions (especially in rural areas), the fact that not all entrepreneurs have their websites, the lack of willingness of businesses to interact with consumers, the lack of qualified personnel in this area, Examples of support for entrepreneurs engaged in certain activities

⁵ <https://ru.wikipedia.org>

⁶ <https://lex.uz/docs/3107036>

⁷ <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/5458249>

⁸There

⁹ <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>

with digital technologies in our country, the lack of specific programs to support them by the state, the lack of integration in the field of education and services.

Today, in implementing the strategy “Digital Uzbekistan - 2030”, it is expedient to identify the shortcomings in providing services to the population with digital technologies.

Based on the above, the main factors influencing the organization of services in the digital economy were studied (Table 1).

Table 1

Factors influencing service delivery in the digital economy¹⁰

s/n	Positive factors	s/n	Negative factors
1	Creation of an organizational and legal framework	1	Restrictions by the state on the development of the sector
2	Availability of funding sources	2	Lack of benefits for those engaged in innovative activities
3	Equipped with digital technology	3	Lack of competitive environment
4	Availability of specialist staff	4	Lack of information for entrepreneurs when starting a business based on digital technologies

The table data analysis mentioned above suggests that it would be expedient to support business entities with directional incentives to start any innovative activity. Today, despite the country’s densely populated urban and district centers being more developed in terms of service, it is possible to observe a low level of use of digital technologies in rural areas.

The analysis shows that despite digital technologies in rural areas, there is a lack of quality mobile services and high-speed Internet networks. This poses some challenges in accessing education services, information and communication services, online ordering, and similar services in rural areas.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that: - Socio-economic development of the population can be achieved in our country by developing services in the digital economy. At the same time, it would be reasonable to train new specialists in this field, develop quality communication services in rural areas, support new businesses on this issue, establish new service enterprises and create jobs in these enterprises.

V. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

The following proposals can be made for the organization of services in the digital economy in our country:

- financing of business entities on credit lines at the expense of available funds of commercial banks in the development of services;

¹⁰The table is based on the author's research.

- state support of business entities to develop service delivery;
- granting preferential terms in the implementation of mandatory payments to businesses operating in rural areas based on digital technologies;
- organization of short-term training and advanced training courses for young entrepreneurs in the field of service, involving higher education specialists and employees of leading service enterprises in this field;
- increase attention to the training of personnel in IT technologies and conduct business trainings with the involvement of specialists from foreign countries in this field.

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